

THLIBOMORPHISMS

CHRISTOPH V. MEYER

ABSTRACT. A generalization for the notion of idempotence of functions is presented in the form of *ignorant functions*. The concept is then applied to squashings between algebras which are ignorant with respect to all operators of their domain algebra. Simpler yet equivalent characterizations of ignorant function are proven.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. **Notation.** Given a function $f: X \rightarrow X$ and a natural number n , the notation f^n is ambiguous, as it could denote either the n -fold composite of f or the n -fold Cartesian product of f . To circumvent this, the exponential notation hereinafter always denotes the composite of a function, so

$$(1) \quad f^n = \underbrace{f \circ \dots \circ f}_{n \text{ times}},$$

while the n -fold Cartesian product of any object A – not just functions – shall be denoted

$$(2) \quad \prod^n A = \underbrace{A \times \dots \times A}_{n \text{ times}}.$$

The symbol δ_{ij} denotes the Kronecker-Delta, which takes the value 1 if $i = j$ and 0 otherwise.

1.2. **Motivation.** Consider a set X and a function $f: X \rightarrow X$. The function f is said to be *idempotent* if $f \circ f = f$. Inductively, this implies $f^n = f$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$. By picking an arbitrary element $x \in X$, we obtain $f^n(x) = f(x)$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, which can be rewritten to

$$(3) \quad f(\text{id}_X(f^n(x))) = f(\text{id}_X(x)) \quad \text{for } n \in \mathbb{N}_0;$$

this means that f can “look through” the function id_X and stay invariant under all images under the latter of $f^n(x)$ for arbitrary $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ but fixed $x \in X$.

This allows for a generalization of the term “idempotence” by simply replacing the function id_X with any other function from a superset of X to a subset of X .

Example 1.1. *Let*

$$(4) \quad \begin{aligned} f: \mathbb{R} &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ x &\mapsto x + 1. \end{aligned}$$

We observe that f preserves the decimal part of its input. To formalize this notion, we define

$$(5) \quad \begin{aligned} g: \mathbb{R} &\rightarrow [0, 1) \\ x &\mapsto x - \lfloor x \rfloor, \end{aligned}$$

which extracts the decimal part of a real number. The function g acts like a “detector” for chains of the form $f^n(x)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $x \in \mathbb{R}$, mapping all such expressions to a unique representative in $[0, 1)$. Thus follows

$$(6) \quad g(f^n(x)) = g(x) \quad \text{for } n \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ and } x \in \mathbb{R}$$

and therefore obviously

$$(7) \quad f(g(f^n(x))) = f(g(x)) \quad \text{for } n \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ and } x \in \mathbb{R}.$$

This example is rather trivial because g itself is already invariant under composition chains of f . It shall be noted that if we insist to find a function g which satisfies (7), it must also satisfy (6), because f is injective and therefore left-cancellative.

FIGURE 1. Visualization of $f(x) = x + 1$ and $g(x) = x - \lfloor x \rfloor$

Let us modify f and g as follows:

$$(8) \quad \begin{aligned} \tilde{f}: \mathbb{R} &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} & \text{and} & & \tilde{g}: \mathbb{R} &\rightarrow [0, 1) \\ x &\mapsto |x| + 1 & & & x &\mapsto \text{sign}(x) \cdot (x - \lfloor x \rfloor). \end{aligned}$$

The function \tilde{f} is no longer injective, as it does not care about the sign of its input; the function \tilde{g} does the same as before while preserving the sign. It is easily verified that $\tilde{g} \circ \tilde{f}^n = \tilde{g}$ is no longer true for all $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ but the condition

$$(9) \quad \tilde{f}(\tilde{g}(\tilde{f}^n(x))) = \tilde{f}(\tilde{g}(x)) \quad \text{for } n \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ and } x \in \mathbb{R}.$$

still holds.

FIGURE 2. Visualization of $\tilde{f}(x) = |x| + 1$ and $\tilde{g}(x) = \text{sign}(x) \cdot (x - \lfloor x \rfloor)$

2. IGNORANT FUNCTIONS

We shall now formalize the idea presented throughout the introduction.

Definition 2.1 (*g-ignorant function for one-dimensional g*). Let X be a set and let

$$(10) \quad f, g: X \rightarrow X$$

be functions. The function f is called *g-ignorant* if

$$(11) \quad f \circ g = f \circ g \circ f^n \quad \text{for all } n \in \mathbb{N}_0.$$

In cases where g is defined as a function from \overline{X} to \underline{X} , where \overline{X} is a superset and \underline{X} is a subset X , we ignore composing g with the technically necessary canonical injections and still refer to f as *g-ignorant* as opposed to $i_{\underline{X} \rightarrow X} \circ g \circ i_{X \rightarrow \overline{X}}$ -ignorant. The same applies vice versa to f .

We allow for a further generalization to multi-dimensional g in order to later discuss ignorance with respect to operators of an algebra.

Definition 2.2 (*g-ignorant function for multi-dimensional g*). Let X be a set, $k \in \mathbb{N}$ be a natural number and let

$$(12) \quad f: X \rightarrow X \quad \text{and} \quad g: \prod_{i=1}^k X \rightarrow X$$

be functions. The function f is called *g-ignorant* if

$$(13) \quad f \circ g = f \circ g \circ \prod_{i=1}^k f^{n_i} \quad \text{for all } n_1, \dots, n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0.$$

First, let us prove the obvious.

Lemma 2.3. Let X be a set and let

$$(14) \quad f: X \rightarrow X$$

be a function. The following statements are equivalent:

- (1) f is id_X -ignorant.
- (2) f is idempotent.

Proof. (1) \implies (2): Let f be id_X -ignorant. Then, $f \circ \text{id}_X = f \circ \text{id}_X \circ f^n$ holds for all $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$; in particular, $f = f \circ \text{id}_X = f \circ \text{id}_X \circ f = f \circ f$.

(2) \implies (1): Let f be idempotent, i.e. $f = f \circ f$. It can easily be obtained through induction that $f = f^n$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$. Thus follows $f \circ \text{id}_X = f = f^{n+1} = f \circ f^n = f \circ \text{id}_X \circ f^n$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$. \square

The next observation aims to ease proving the ignorance of a function. It suffices to show that a function f is g -ignorant in each argument separately and only for a single application of f to that argument.

Lemma 2.4. *Let X be a set, $k \in \mathbb{N}$ be a natural number and let*

$$(15) \quad f: X \rightarrow X \quad \text{and} \quad g: \prod_{i=1}^k X \rightarrow X$$

be functions. Then, the following statements are equivalent:

- (1) f is g -ignorant.
- (2) $f \circ g = f \circ g \circ \prod_{i=1}^k q^{\delta_{ij}}$ for all $1 \leq j \leq k$.

Proof. (1) \implies (2): Let f be g -ignorant and $1 \leq j \leq k$ be arbitrary. Per definitionem, $f \circ g$ is equal to $f \circ g \circ \prod_{i=1}^k f^{n_i}$ for all $n_1, \dots, n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, in particular for $n_i := \delta_{ij}$, where $1 \leq i \leq k$.

(2) \implies (1): Let $f \circ g = f \circ g \circ \prod_{i=1}^k q^{\delta_{ij}}$ apply for all $1 \leq j \leq k$ and let $n_1, \dots, n_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ be arbitrary. We will only consider the first argument of g , i.e. show

$$(16) \quad f \circ g = f \circ g \circ \left(f^{n_1} \times \prod_{i=2}^{k-1} \text{id}_X \right) \text{ inductively;}$$

the process can be repeated for all arguments. For $n_1 = 1$, it follows:

$$(17) \quad f \circ g = f \circ g \circ \left(\prod_{i=1}^k \text{id}_X \right) = f \circ g \circ \left(\prod_{i=1}^k q^0 \right) = f \circ g \circ \left(\prod_{i=1}^k q^{\delta_{i1}} \right)$$

$$(18) \quad = f \circ g \circ \left(f \times \prod_{i=2}^k q^{\delta_{i1}} \right) = f \circ g \circ \left(f \times \prod_{i=2}^{k-1} q^0 \right) = f \circ g \circ \left(f \times \prod_{i=2}^{k-1} \text{id}_X \right).$$

For arbitrary n_1 , assume that the claim has already been proven. It follows:

$$(19) \quad f \circ g = f \circ g \circ \left(f^{n_1} \times \prod_{i=2}^{k-1} \text{id}_X \right) = (f \circ g) \circ \left(f^{n_1} \times \prod_{i=2}^{k-1} \text{id}_X \right)$$

$$(20) \quad = \left(f \circ g \circ \left(f \times \prod_{i=2}^{k-1} \text{id}_X \right) \right) \circ \left(f^{n_1} \times \prod_{i=2}^{k-1} \text{id}_X \right)$$

$$(21) \quad = f \circ g \circ \left(f^{n_1+1} \times \prod_{i=2}^{k-1} \text{id}_X \right).$$

\square

3. THLIBOMORPHISMS

Instead of looking at arbitrary functions, let us now narrow the view to squashings [Mey25, Definition 1.8] between algebras and operators of those algebras.

Let $\mathbf{A} = (A, (f_{\mathbf{A}})_{f \in \mathcal{F}})$ be an algebra of type (\mathcal{F}, σ) [Ihr93, Definition 1.1.3] and $\mathbf{B} = (B, (f_{\mathbf{B}})_{f \in \mathcal{G}})$ be an algebra of type (\mathcal{G}, τ) squashable with respect to \mathbf{A} [Mey25, Definition 1.7]. Consider a squashing q from \mathbf{B} onto \mathbf{A} . Because squashings are also functions, we may talk about the $f_{\mathbf{B}}$ -ignorance of q for some $f \in \mathcal{G}$. Squashings which are ignorant with respect to all operators of \mathbf{B} will be of particular interest.

Definition 3.1 (Thlibomorphism). *Let $\mathbf{A} = (A, (f_{\mathbf{A}})_{f \in \mathcal{F}})$ be an algebra of type (\mathcal{F}, σ) and $\mathbf{B} = (B, (f_{\mathbf{B}})_{f \in \mathcal{G}})$ be an algebra of type (\mathcal{G}, τ) squashable with respect to \mathbf{A} . A squashing q from \mathbf{B} onto \mathbf{A} is called a thlibomorphism if it is $f_{\mathbf{B}}$ -ignorant for all $f \in \mathcal{G}$.*

Lemma 2.4 can be refined for thlibomorphisms specifically; instead of considering each argument of an operator $f_{\mathbf{B}}$ separately, it suffices to show the equivalence of $q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}}$ to the composite of the latter with the $\tau(f)$ -fold Cartesian product of q , effectively applying q once to every argument.

Theorem 3.2. *Let $\mathbf{A} = (A, (f_{\mathbf{A}})_{f \in \mathcal{F}})$ be an algebra of type (\mathcal{F}, σ) and $\mathbf{B} = (B, (f_{\mathbf{B}})_{f \in \mathcal{G}})$ be an algebra of type (\mathcal{G}, τ) squashable with respect to \mathbf{A} . Let q be a squashing from \mathbf{B} onto \mathbf{A} . Then, the following statements are equivalent:*

- (1) q is a thlibomorphism.
- (2) $q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} = q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} \circ \prod_{i=1}^{\tau(f)} q^{n_i}$ for all $f \in \mathcal{G}$ and $n_1, \dots, n_{\tau(f)} \in \mathbb{N}_0$, i.e. the following diagram commutes:

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 \prod^{\tau(f)} B & & & & \\
 \downarrow \prod_{i=1}^{\tau(f)} q^{n_i} & \searrow f_{\mathbf{B}} & & & \\
 \prod^{\tau(f)} B & & B & & \\
 \downarrow & & \searrow q & & \\
 \prod^{\tau(f)} B & \xrightarrow{f_{\mathbf{B}}} & B & \xrightarrow{q} & A.
 \end{array}$$

- (3) $q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} = q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} \circ \prod_{i=1}^{\tau(f)} q^{\delta_{ij}}$ for all $f \in \mathcal{G}$ and $1 \leq j \leq \tau(f)$, i.e. the following diagram commutes:

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 \prod^{\tau(f)} B & & & & \\
 \downarrow \prod_{i=1}^{\tau(f)} q^{\delta_{ik}} & \searrow f_{\mathbf{B}} & & & \\
 \prod^{\tau(f)} B & & B & & \\
 \downarrow & & \searrow q & & \\
 \prod^{\tau(f)} B & \xrightarrow{f_{\mathbf{B}}} & B & \xrightarrow{q} & A.
 \end{array}$$

- (4) $q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} = q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} \circ \prod^{\tau(f)} q$ for all $f \in \mathcal{G}$, i.e. the following diagram commutes:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
\prod^{\tau(f)} B & & \\
\downarrow \Pi^{\tau(f)} q & \searrow f_{\mathbf{B}} & \\
\prod^{\tau(f)} B & & B \\
\downarrow & & \searrow q \\
\prod^{\tau(f)} B & \xrightarrow{f_{\mathbf{B}}} & B \xrightarrow{q} A.
\end{array}$$

Proof. (1) \iff (2): Per definitionem.

(2) \iff (3): According to Lemma 2.4.

(2) \implies (4): Follows directly from statement (2) by choosing $n_1 \equiv \dots \equiv n_{\tau(f)} := 1$.

(4) \implies (3): Let $q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} = q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} \circ \prod^{\tau(f)} q$ apply for all $f \in \mathcal{G}$. Let $1 \leq j \leq \tau(f)$ be arbitrary. Due to the idempotence of squashings [Mey25, Lemma 2.4], it follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
(22) \quad & q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} = q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} \circ \prod^{\tau(f)} q \\
(23) \quad & = q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} \circ \left(\prod_{i=1}^{j-1} q \times q \times \prod_{i=j+1}^{\tau(f)} q \right) \\
(24) \quad & = q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} \circ \left(\prod_{i=1}^{j-1} q \times q^2 \times \prod_{i=j+1}^{\tau(f)} q \right) \\
(25) \quad & = q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} \circ \left(\prod_{i=1}^{j-1} q \times q \times \prod_{i=j+1}^{\tau(f)} q \right) \circ \left(\prod_{i=1}^{j-1} \text{id}_B \times q \times \prod_{i=j+1}^{\tau(f)} \text{id}_B \right) \\
(26) \quad & = q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} \circ \prod^{\tau(f)} q \circ \left(\prod_{i=1}^{j-1} \text{id}_B \times q \times \prod_{i=j+1}^{\tau(f)} \text{id}_B \right) \\
(27) \quad & = q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} \circ \left(\prod_{i=1}^{j-1} \text{id}_B \times q \times \prod_{i=j+1}^{\tau(f)} \text{id}_B \right) \\
(28) \quad & = q \circ f_{\mathbf{B}} \circ \prod_{i=1}^{\tau(f)} q^{\delta_{ij}}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

Example 3.3. (1) Same universe, different types: *Similar to the forgetful functor $U: \mathbf{Rng} \rightarrow \mathbf{Ab}$ between the categories of (small) rings and (small) Abelian groups [ML98, p. 14], we define a forgetful squashing*

$$(29) \quad \begin{aligned}
q: R &\rightarrow R \\
x &\mapsto x
\end{aligned}$$

from a given ring $(R, +, \cdot, 0, 1, \bullet^{-1})$ to its underlying Abelian group $(R, +, 0, \bullet^{-1})$. Clearly, q is equal to id_R and therefore a thlibomorphism. In fact, all squashings between two algebras which share the same universe

must be the identity function in order to satisfy $q|_R = \text{id}_R$ [Mey25, Definition 1.8].

- (2) Different universes, same type: Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$ be a natural number and $(G_j, +_j, e_j, \bullet_j^{-1})$ be groups for $1 \leq j \leq k$. Let $(\tilde{G}_j, +, e, \bullet^{-1})$, $1 \leq j \leq k$, denote the isomorphic groups with

$$(30) \quad \tilde{G}_j := \prod_{i=1}^{j-1} \{e_i\} \times G_j \times \prod_{i=j+1}^k \{e_i\}$$

$$(31) \quad + := \prod_{i=1}^k +_i$$

$$(32) \quad e := (e_1, \dots, e_k)$$

$$(33) \quad \bullet^{-1} := \prod_{i=1}^k \bullet_i^{-1}.$$

For each $1 \leq j \leq k$, the “quasi-projection”

$$(34) \quad \begin{aligned} \pi_j : \prod_{i=1}^k G_i &\rightarrow \tilde{G}_j \\ (a_1, \dots, a_k) &\mapsto (e_1, \dots, e_{j-1}, a_j, e_{j+1}, \dots, e_k) \end{aligned}$$

constitutes a thlibomorphism from the group $(\prod_{i=1}^k G_i, +, e, \bullet^{-1})$ to the group $(\tilde{G}_j, +, e, \bullet^{-1})$ (proof as exercise).

- (3) Different universes, same type: Let $(R, +, \cdot, 0, 1, \bullet^{-1})$ be a ring and let $(R[t], +, \cdot, 0, 1, \bullet^{-1})$ be the polynomial ring over R in the indeterminate t [Bou74, III, § 2, No. 9]. Furthermore, let $x \in R$ be some element of R . We define the evaluation map φ_x as follows:

$$(35) \quad \begin{aligned} \varphi_x : R[t] &\rightarrow R \\ p &\mapsto p(x). \end{aligned}$$

Each element in R can be identified with its respective constant polynomial in $R[t]$, so $R \subseteq R[t]$; together with the fact that both rings are algebras of the same type, we conclude that $(R[t], +, \cdot, 0, 1, \bullet^{-1})$ is squashable with respect to $(R, +, \cdot, 0, 1, \bullet^{-1})$. Moreover, φ_x maps each constant polynomial to the respective constant in R , so $\varphi_x|_R = \text{id}_R$; this means that φ_x is a squashing. One can easily convince oneself of the truth of the following statements for arbitrary $p_1, p_2 \in R[t]$:

$$(36) \quad \varphi_x(p_1 + p_2) = \varphi_x(p_1) + \varphi_x(p_2) = \varphi_x(\varphi_x(p_1) + \varphi_x(p_2))$$

$$(37) \quad \varphi_x(p_1 \cdot p_2) = \varphi_x(p_1) \cdot \varphi_x(p_2) = \varphi_x(\varphi_x(p_1) \cdot \varphi_x(p_2))$$

$$(38) \quad \varphi_x(p_1^{-1}) = \varphi_x(p_1)^{-1} = \varphi_x(\varphi_x(p_1)^{-1});$$

by Theorem 3.2 (4), φ_x is a thlibomorphism.

- (4) Different universes, different types: Let $\mathbf{T}(X)$ be a recursion operator extensible term algebra over X [Mey25, Definition 3.2] and $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}(X))$ be the recursion operator extension of $\mathbf{T}(X)$ [Mey25, Definition 3.3].

We want to apply Theorem 3.2 (3) to the standard squashing q_X [Mey25, Definition 3.6]. With respect to all operators except the recursion operator,

the ignorance of q_X is trivial. For the recursion operator, the ignorance can be deduced from [Mey25, Lemma 3.20] in the first argument (initial value) and from [Mey25, Lemma 3.21] in the third argument (recursion rule). We observe that the natural cardinality [Mey25, Definition 3.22] remains invariant under the standard squashing because q_X is applied upon determining the existence of a predecessor [Mey25, Definition 3.7] either way and q_X is idempotent [Mey25, Lemma 2.4]. Thus, the image of a term under the standard squashing lies in the same natural congruence class [Mey25, Definition 3.25] as the term itself, which implies the ignorance of q_X in the second argument (recursion depth) of the recursion operator by [Mey25, Theorem 3.32].

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RUPRECHT-KARLS-UNIVERSITÄT HEIDELBERG
Email address: christoph.meyer(at)stud.uni-heidelberg.de